

STAC for CEDA - Developing a scalable, standards-based search system

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Introduction

The Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) is based in the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)'s RAL Space department. We support environmental science research through the development and management of services that aid in the curation and analysis of environmental data. Our primary services are the CEDA archive, a long-term data store of atmospheric and Earth observation data and JASMIN, a data-intensive supercomputer which provides the infrastructure for CEDA's services and supports the data analysis requirements for our user community (Lawrence et al., 2013).

The CEDA archive hosts over 20 Petabytes of data, principally for the UK environmental science community. Sources for this data include aircraft campaigns, satellites, automatic weather stations, climate models, and many others. Additionally, different providers and projects favour different file formats.

Our data holding also spans storage types. Infrequently used and oversized data is stored on tape, for energy and financial efficiency reasons. The online section of our data holdings is stored on scale-out storage and made available through a POSIX interface to local clusters and simple HTTP and FTP services for download. In total, there are over 8000 datasets, containing over 350 million files in the archive. Users can search these datasets through the CEDA catalogue which links to a directory hierarchy for data access.

In recent years we have also generated a complete index of the archive's files, our File Based Index (FBI). The FBI contains basic information about files including sizes, checksums and a limited set of metadata extracted from the data files. Summaries from the FBI are fed upwards to the discovery records in the catalogue.

The Problem

Several issues exist in the current cataloguing at the file level. Firstly, the heterogeneity of the data in format, mixed storage media, and science domains mean that workflows to do uniform metadata extraction are patchy. Secondly, the scale of the archive is such that any metadata extraction processes require very robust and performant workflows. Finally, we are currently missing some critical information at the file level, including spatio-temporal information.

The heterogeneity and scale of the archive are illustrated in Figure 1. Just over 40% of the files in the CEDA Archive are in NetCDF format, but many other formats are also used, including historical data where the format is not immediately identifiable from the filename or extension (Rew and Davis, 1990). Even in the preferred NetCDF format, there are many sub-conventions that need to be accommodated to fully describe the data.

Fig 1. Panel 1: Distribution of file types in the CEDA archive. Panel 2: Dataset size of the archive. Colours indicate the percentage of files in the dataset parameter information at the file level.

To compensate for the missing metadata at the file level several domain-specific tools have been developed and provide spatio-temporal discovery. For example, the EUFAR flight finder allows users to find data from research aircraft flights and Earth System Grid Federation interfaces facilitate the use of climate datasets. These services focus on one area of the archive which is more homogeneous, and therefore, the metadata being extracted is richer and more valuable. Nevertheless, this only covers a small section of the archive. Given the size and diversity of our data, it would not be feasible to create similar novel solutions for all stored data.

Current workflows

As files are deposited in the archive, metadata is extracted for each file and the result is recorded in the FBI as a JSON document. We call this process “indexing on deposit”. If we need to re-index all the files, perhaps because the metadata extraction has been updated, then a “Crawler” process is initiated that will queue the whole archive for re-processing.

Only 48% of datasets in the CEDA Archive have automatically extracted metadata information by this method. There are a variety of causes for this missing metadata, including files being unreachable (offline, removed, external), file type incompatibility, or the metadata itself being incorrect, missing, or not standardised.

Method

This project aimed to find a pragmatic and generalised solution to file-level metadata that would allow us to expose the bulk of the CEDA Archive, via rich faceted and free-text search. To achieve this both general and dataset-specific metadata would need to be extracted from the full breadth of the archive. Furthermore, it would need to be performant at the scale of, and be able to grow in parallel with, the archive. Additionally, any solution should make the creation of new and existing user interfaces and search services simpler, and facilitate interoperability with user tools and our partners in national and international collaborations.

STAC

As far as possible we wanted to use existing standards. This would not only allow for the use of available tools and software but it was hoped that it could foster collaboration with other organisations that faced similar challenges. Such a standard would need to be flexible enough to accommodate the diversity of the data and be simple enough that it would be viable at the scale of the archive.

STAC (Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog) is designed to be minimalistic with the core specification requiring only space and time, on a latitude and longitude grid in the standard Julian calendar (Holmes, 2017). It provides a well-defined, developer-friendly, JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) Application Programming Interface (API). The standard was developed with the Earth Observation community as the primary beneficiary. And as members of the Earth observation, atmospheric science, and Earth system modelling communities as well as for our own interests, we were interested to see whether STAC could fit our needs.

The base element of STAC is the *Asset* which STAC defines as “*any file that represents information about the earth captured in a certain space and time*”. These are then grouped into *Items* which are required to have both a spatial and temporal value. In addition, any other information associated with the item can be stored as a facet value pair in the item’s “properties”. Items can then be further grouped into *Catalogs* which “*provides a structure to organise and browse STAC Items*”. Finally, catalogues can be extended to form *Collections* by including additional information, including a summary of their items.

On top of the core STAC framework, the STAC community has already begun developing a range of tools and extensions. We felt some existing extensions may be usable within areas of the archive, for example, the Landsat extension (USGC, 2022). Additionally, we thought that further extensions could be developed where needed. Finally, as STAC was being actively developed we saw an opportunity for collaboration. For these reasons, we began working on a STAC implementation at CEDA to see if it could meet our requirements.

Fig 2. Panel 1: Visual representation of the STAC Generator configuration. Panel 2: An example Collection Description.

STAC at CEDA

We aim to create a full-stack software implementation, including an indexing framework, API server, clients, and vocabulary management. Where possible the system was to be kept flexible. This would allow it to be used across CEDA's data holdings and be more adaptable to future data and requirement changes. Additionally, it is hoped that this flexibility will mean the produced software is reusable by other organisations.

The initial challenge we faced was generating the necessary metadata needed for a STAC catalog. This led us to develop the "STAC Generator", which can be used to generate STAC Assets, Items, and Collections (CEDA, 2021). The plugin architecture employed allows the input, output, and the type of object generated (Asset, Item, Collection) to be configured based on the use case, see Figure 2.1, and therefore increasing the code's reusability (Sun et al., 2015). Additionally, new requirements can be met by the addition of new plugins which it is hoped will reduce the required changes to the core code (Rashid et al., 2010).

Because we needed the extracted metadata to be specific to the dataset the extraction methods are handled in their own configuration, see Figure 2.2. This configuration, known as the collection description, specifies which extraction methods to use. Which collection description is used for a given Asset, Item, or Collection is chosen by information from the input plugin, enabling specific extraction methods to be chosen for the different areas of the archive.

Similarly, the method of ID generation for each STAC level can be configured in the collection descriptions. For example, the hash method generates the ID from a dot-separated list of facets that the user has specified, which allows for novel groupings of assets and items.

For the STAC Generator to be a viable solution it would need to be able to extract the necessary metadata for the entire archive in a *reasonable* time. Additionally, the search of this data must also be able to be conducted in a *reasonable* time. To accurately test this a full scan of the archive was planned. With the help of our data curators, we wrote an initial set of collection descriptions. Whilst most of these were specific to a project within the archive, such as CMIP6, one collection description was written to catch *all the other data* (abbreviated to "ATOD"). Initially, the files covered by the ATOD collection description would have only their file (size, extension, etc) and directory information extracted. To perform the initial scan of the archive we utilised CEDA's Batch Compute system, to allow generators to be run in parallel. The generated metadata was fed into an ElasticSearch cluster, a NoSQL database, chosen for its scalability and search capabilities (Leavitt, 2010).

Fig 3. Panel 1: Dataset with STAC coverage and percentage of files with properties. Panel 2: Dataset with STAC with dataset-specific properties

Once the initial scan was complete the generators would also need to cope with the ingestion of new data. To integrate into our operational data streams, another application, the STAC Stocktake, was developed. As new data is added to our archive it is ingested into the file-based index (FBI). The stac-stocktake periodically checks that the Asset index and the FBI are in sync and adds the appropriate messages to a set of RabbitMQ queues if changes are required. An instance of the STAC Generator then reads from this queue and makes the necessary additions, updates, or removals to the Asset index. A similar approach is used to update the Item and Collection indexes. Any changes to the Asset and Item indexes are tracked by the STAC Stocktake and relevant messages are queued for the STAC Generators.

At the start of the project, the existing STAC API was backed by a PostgreSQL database. As we had chosen to use an Elasticsearch database, we have developed an Elasticsearch backed version of the API. We have followed the STAC API specification developing methods for the core functionality and several of the core and community-made extensions (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2017). In addition, we have developed several of our own extensions to meet the requirements that were not already fulfilled (Smith, 2019). These include free-text search, which allows users to supply a query string as well as facets for search, asset-level search which extends the search to the file level, and the "queryables" extension which gives information on the facets that can be searched on.

Alongside this activity, for ESGF, we have prepared a complete index of some of our climate modelling data mirroring the legacy ESGF search services which our new STAC-based system will replace. This work has included a new dedicated ESGF STAC client which builds on top of pySTAC and integrates CEDA's API extensions. We are working with the ESGF community to migrate the distributed infrastructure to use the new search API.

Results

The initial scan of the archive took ~2 weeks to complete and generated ~325 million assets, ~4 million items and 10 collections. This has produced a minimum viable product style catalogue, with all of the generated assets, items, and collections having at least a base level of metadata, see Figure 3.1. However, this doesn't yet reach the level extracted in the current catalogue, with only 12% having dataset-specific metadata, see Figure 3.2. The metadata richness can be increased in two ways, firstly, by increasing the amount extracted within ATOD. And secondly, through reducing the proportion of the archive ATOD covers by adding more collection descriptions for specific areas.

Preliminary testing of the elasticsearch indexes search speeds found that simple faceted search queries took ~50ms and free-text search ~1-2s, which given the indexes have not yet been tuned for search performance it was felt these times were reasonable.

DKRZ, another climate research centre, has rolled out a deployment of the STAC Generator and the elasticsearch-backed STAC API system for their own data holdings (Wachsmann, 2023). This, along with CEDA's experiments, displays the versatility of STAC, the STAC Generator, and its ability to work within different workflows.

Conclusions

Question	Answer
Can STAC be used as a general model for environmental data search?	✓
Can we generate the metadata required for STAC?	✓
Are we able to <i>quickly</i> search on the generated metadata?	✓
Does STAC have all the functionality we need?	✗
Can we extend STAC to meet our requirements?	✓
Do we need layers in our framework?	?
Could Temporal and Spatial information be optional?	?
Can we use STAC extensions for specific parts of our archive?	?
Do we need Asset Search?	?

Over the course of the last eighteen months, we have reviewed and analysed the STAC standard and concluded that it can be used as a general model for highly heterogeneous environmental data. The required metadata can be generated with the STAC Generator at a viable speed to sustain index on deposit and crawler workflows. The search, through a combination of the STAC API and Elasticsearch, has been seen to work at the scale of the archive and within a reasonable time.

However, there are requirements that STAC did not fulfil, such as multilevel search. We have been able to use STAC's extensibility to begin to meet these needs. But there is still more work needed, for example, many of the projects stored at CEDA have specific vocabularies of terms which categorise data. To reduce the need for new users to understand exact terms, CEDA's STAC catalogue and API will be integrated with a vocabulary server that will allow search on both data collection-specific and general vocabulary terms.

Finally, there are many questions that have not yet been answered. For instance, are 3 levels (asset, item, collection) right for CEDA? Could the core of STAC be further reduced to make Temporal and Spatial information optional? Can different STAC extensions be used for different parts of a catalogue? Do we need Asset-level search?

CEDA will pursue a full operational implementation for STAC to deliver search capability for the entire archive. It is also exploring whether it is a suitable base for the replacement for discovery interfaces of the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), one of our international collaborations. We have expanded our trial to other UK Natural Environment Research Council Data Centres to see if we can broaden the science domain further.

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